

Modeling Language Process as Hierarchical Adaptive Random Distributions

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Abstract

Modeling the process of language is particularly challenging due to its complex nature and the continuous changes required to ensure its relevance. The process of constructing words from a set of characters or sentences from a set of words, among others, is intrinsically hierarchical and conditional. Consequently, we conceptualize the design as recursive, where each level of the process depends on the outcomes of the lower level, and so on. At each level, the process can be seen as a random experiment which involves sequentially selecting one item at a time until a terminal item is reached, where each item is itself a random experiment to be constructed at the lower level. Given that each experiment is inherently conditional, we primarily model this process in discrete intervals. Then at each trial of the experiment, we characterize the selection probability on observed outcomes from previous trials. This enables us to analyze when a specific item is most likely to occur and how the selection probability evolves over successive trials. The cost of the estimation step is reduced through sampling. Finally, the estimation of the variance of the parameter estimate is provided.

Key Words: Artificial neuron network, Computer translation, Cost reduction, Multinomial distribution, Variance estimation.

1. Introduction

An oral and written language is a system based on vocabulary that conveys thoughts, ideas, emotions, and information. Vocabulary refers to a set of words, each with a specific meaning, comprising a series of characters or alphabets. Language facilitates human communication and evolves through changes in vocabulary and syntax to enhance human interaction.

Modeling the process of language is challenging due to the diverse factors that contribute to its continuous development. Among these factors, we identify: (1) the introduction of new grammatical rules to make

communication more efficient; (2) interactions between different languages, which introduce new words, phrases, and ideas; and (3) continuous refinements to ensure language remains relevant.

McCullough and Pitts (1943) and Rosenblatt (1957, 1958), inspired by the function of biological neurons, presented an elegant approach called Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) to teach computers to perform tasks based on observed realizations, termed “examples.” This approach has recently produced the best results in artificial intelligence, including language modeling. The first and simplest ANN is the perceptron, designed to take a number of binary inputs and produce a single binary output. It assigns different weights to each input based on importance and compares the weighted sum with a threshold to generate a binary result. The perceptron represents the first step in ANN development. Modern ANN models have a general structure as follows: (1) Input layer: receives input data and transfers it to the first hidden layer using an initial set of weights. The number of nodes in the input layer corresponds to the number of input data points; (2) Hidden layers: each hidden layer (h , where $h = 1, \dots, H$) processes data from the previous layer and transfers it to the next layer using its own set of weights. The number of hidden layers as well as the number of neurons in each hidden layer are arbitrary; (3) Output layer: receives data from the final hidden layer (H) and produces results using an activation function instead of a threshold. The number of nodes in the output layer depends on the model's intended output. During the weight-estimation process, known as “training,” the weights are adjusted through backpropagation and the gradient descent method by minimizing the error between actual and predicted values. To illustrate the scale of modern ANN, we consider the widely known model, Generative Pre-trained Transformer 4. It consists of approximately 100 layers, 100 billion neurons, and over 100 trillion parameters or synapses. The training dataset comprises over 10 trillion words. The training cost exceeds \$50 million, excluding researcher salaries, and the process takes more than 50 days. Note that a billion is 1,000 million, and a trillion is 1,000 billion.

Although the ANN cookbook approach is simple and appealing, it lacks theoretical justification and demands significant computational resources. While intensive research continues in the field of ANN with adequate resources, it is also essential to explore simpler and more rigorous methods that may both reduce costs and improve efficiency. In Section 2, we propose a theoretically grounded alternative approach. We begin by describing the method at a single level of the recursive process, subsequently introduce the hierarchical structure, and conclude with a discussion of the adaptive procedure developed in response to observed outcomes. In Section 3, we present the proposed sampling design for a language, detailing the method for the estimating equation, model parameter estimation, variance derivation and estimation and sample size determination.

2. Proposed Approach

Section 2.1 introduces the single-level approach. Subsequently, Section 2.2 examines the relationship between two levels. Finally, Section 2.3 briefly discusses the integration of the observed value as an explanatory variable.

2.1 Scheme for One level

Suppose a finite population $\mathbf{M}^{(l)}$ is made up of $M^{(l)}$ elements at level l . For the first level, i.e. $l = 1$, the population $\mathbf{M}^{(1)}$ is the set of all the characters that constitute a language, for the second level i.e. $l = 2$, the population $\mathbf{M}^{(2)}$ is the set of all words that constitute a language, etc. For the sake of clarity, we suppress the superscript, and we represent the population for a certain level by \mathbf{M} . To each element i of the population \mathbf{M} is associated a vector \mathbf{x}_i of explanatory variables that characterize the element. Note that if we use the superscript notation, then the index $i^{(1)}$ refers to a character, the index $i^{(2)}$ refers to a word, and the index $i^{(3)}$ refers to a sentence, etc. Consider a random experiment k on the population \mathbf{M} , which consists on the selection of one element from eligible elements at each trial t , $t=1, 2, \dots$ until we get an achievement where success consists on choosing an eligible specific item, say a stopping item s , at trial t from a set of specific elements of the population, in which case the length of the experiment k is equal to $m_k = t$, with $m_k > 1$. This experiment is based on three main assumptions: (1) The trials being conducted with replacement; (2) There can only be one selected element of each trial; and, (3) The random experiment stops when one of the ending or stopping elements is selected. The set of stopping elements constitutes a subset \mathbf{M}_s of \mathbf{M} , with $\mathbf{M}_s \subset \mathbf{M}$. Let us denote a typical item of these stopping elements by s . The result of the random experiment k is a string \mathbf{r}_k composed of an ordered sequence of length m_k of eligible elements of population \mathbf{M} , with the last element is equal to a stopping element.

Let $e_i^{(t|M)}$ be the eligibility indicator for element i at trial t , i.e. $e_i^{(t|M)} = 1$ if element i is eligible for selection at trial t and $e_i^{(t|M)} = 0$ if not, and $q_i^{(t|M)}$ be the conditional probability that element i is eligible given some explanatory variables and the observed data. For each trial t of an experiment, we have $M^{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^M e_i^{(t|M)}$ possible mutually exclusive outcomes. Let $I_i^{(t|M)}$ be the conditional selection indicator for eligible element i at trial t , i.e. $I_i^{(t|M)} = 1 | e_i^{(t|M)} = 1$ if the eligible element i is selected at trial t and $I_i^{(t|M)} = 0 | e_i^{(t|M)} = 1$ if not. Note that $I_i^{(t|M)} = 0$ for ineligible elements ($e_i^{(t|M)} = 0$). The selection

probability $p_i^{(t|M)}$ is defined as the conditional probability that element i will be selected at trial t given its eligibility, the population \mathbf{M} , and some explanatory variables.

We consider the random variable $o_i^{(t|M)} = e_i^{(t|M)} I_i^{(t|M)}$ that is formed as the product of the two random variables $e_i^{(t|M)}$ and $I_i^{(t|M)}$. We have $E(o_i^{(t|M)}) = q_i^{(t|M)} p_i^{(t|M)} \equiv g_i^{(t|M)}$, $Var(o_i^{(t|M)}) = g_i^{(t|M)}(1 - g_i^{(t|M)})$, and for $j \neq i$ $Cov(o_i^{(t|M)}, o_j^{(t|M)}) = -g_i^{(t|M)} g_j^{(t|M)}$.

Since the $M^{(t)}$ outcomes are mutually exclusive and one must occur, we have $\sum_{i=1}^M o_i^{(t|M)} = 1$. Suppose the random variable \mathbf{R}_k describes the results of the experiment k . We have

$$\Pr(\mathbf{R}_k = \mathbf{r}_k) = \prod_{t=1}^{m_k} f(r_k^{(t)}) \equiv f(\mathbf{r}_k), \quad (2.1)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_k = (r_k^{(1)}, \dots, r_k^{(m_k)})$ is the observed string result and m_k is the length of \mathbf{r}_k .

2.2 Hieratical Aspect

Let's discuss now what is the marginal probability $g_i^{(t)}$ of choosing an element i at a given level at trial t . The population \mathbf{M} at a given level is the set of all results of the lower level. At the first level ($l = 1$), the population \mathbf{M} is the set of characters that form a language, and the marginal probability of choosing an element i at trial t is

$$g_i^{(t)} = g_i^{(t|M)}.$$

At higher level (e.g. $l = 2$), the marginal probability of choosing an element i resulting from experiment k is composed of two components.

$$g_i^{(t)} = g_i^{(t|M)} \times f^{(l)}(\mathbf{r}_i).$$

The first component $g_i^{(t|M)}$ is the conditional probability of choosing the element given that the lower level has been already selected and observed, and the second component $f^{(l)}(\mathbf{r}_i)$ is the probability of choosing the string i at the lower level (e.g. $l = 1$), given by (2.1). Note that for the first level $f^{(l)}(\mathbf{r}_i) = 1$ for any character i , unless multiple languages are studied simultaneously.

2.3 Influence of Explanatory Variables on Probabilities

Let $h_i^{(t|M)}$ be either $q_i^{(t|M)}$ or $p_i^{(t|M)}$. We express the inverse link function of the conditional probability as a function of the explanatory variables \mathbf{v}_i and a vector of parameters $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ to be estimated. For example at the first level when studying the English language, \mathbf{v}_i may contained dummy variables to indicate some characteristics of English language characters: some or all the twenty-one consonants, the five vowels (a,

e, i, o, u), and some or all the sixteen punctuation marks, such as periods, question marks, exclamation points, commas, etc. At the second level, \mathbf{v}_i may contain dummy variables to represent some characteristics of different types of words in the English language, such as nouns, pronouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. At each trial, dummy variable can also be used to characterize sentence structure, which refers to how words are arranged in a sentence. This includes the order of words and how they form a complete thought. In English, the basic structure consists of a subject and predicate. The subject performs the action as the noun and the predicate describes that action as the verb.

For the first trial of a given level, the inverse link form of the probability is expressed as

$$\varphi^{-1}(h_i^{(1|M)}) = \eta(\mathbf{v}_i^{(1)}, \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(1)}), \quad (2.2)$$

for known function $\eta(\cdot)$, where $\mathbf{v}_i^{(1)}$ is an appropriate vector of explanatory variables, $\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(1)}$ is the associated unknown vector parameter to be estimated, and $\varphi(\cdot)$ is a link function – although the link function is generally used to transform (or to link) the conditional mean to the linear predictor $\mathbf{v}_i^{(1)T} \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(1)}$. For example, $\varphi(a) = a$ with $\eta(\mathbf{v}_i^{(1)}, \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(1)}) = \mathbf{v}_i^{(1)T} \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(1)}$ gives a linear regression model and $\varphi(a) = \exp(a)/\{1 + \exp(a)\}$ with $\eta(\mathbf{v}_i^{(1)}, \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(1)}) = \mathbf{v}_i^{(1)T} \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(1)}$ gives a logistic regression model for binary responses.

Additional influences on probability can be investigated by adding further predictors to the initial probability model. For instance, the probability at the second trial, $t = 2$, differs from the model in (2.2) by the inclusion of the time-variant observed indicator $\delta^{(2|j)} = \max\{e_1^{(1)}I_1^{(1)}, \dots, e_M^{(1)}I_M^{(1)}\}$, the influence of which is captured by the parameter $\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(2|j)} = \sum_{j=1}^M e_j^{(1)}I_j^{(1)} \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(2|j)}$:

$$\varphi^{-1}(h_i^{(2|M)}) = \eta(\mathbf{v}_i^{(2)}, \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(2)}),$$

where $\mathbf{v}_i^{(2)} = (\mathbf{v}_i^{(1)}, \delta^{(2|j)})^T$, $\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(2)} = (\boldsymbol{\phi}^{(1)T}, \boldsymbol{\phi}^{(2|j)T})^T$ is the vector parameter to be estimated, and J is the index of the maximum element or the index of the precedent selected element.

3. Sampling and Processing a Language

A language can be conceptualized as a vast collection of different book genres, ranging from adventure fiction to self-help literature. Each book is organized into chapters, each chapter into sections, each section into sentences, each sentence into words, and each word into letters. This structure can be envisioned in survey design as a stratified multistage cluster sampling process, where stratification reflects the genre and other relevant characteristics, and the multistage clusters correspond to chapters, sections, sentences, and words. Sampling without replacement is favored over sampling with replacement due to its greater

efficiency; however, computing an unbiased estimator of variance becomes computationally intensive under multistage cluster designs.

To address this challenge while respecting the hierarchical structure, we propose selecting independent (stratified) single-stage cluster samples at each level of the process. For instance, in the construction of words, a cluster sample of sentences is drawn from the population of all (stratified) sentences, with each sentence representing a cluster of words. Every element (i.e., word) within each selected sentence is then processed. This approach accounts for both the relationship between a sentence and the words that compose it, the relationships among words within a sentence, and the relationship between words and their constituent letters. Similarly, for the construction of sentences, an independent (stratified) cluster sample of chapters is selected from the population of chapters, with each chapter representing a cluster of sentences. Every element (i.e., sentence) within each selected chapter is then processed. This approach balances efficiency and simplicity, facilitating practical implementation without compromising the structural dependencies inherent in the data.

Section 3.1 introduces estimating equation under single-stage cluster sampling. Subsequently, Section 3.2 examines model parameter estimation. Section 3.3 present variance derivation and estimation method. Finally, Section 3.4 examines sample size determination.

3.1 Estimating Equation

Under cluster sampling, the weighted estimating equation (EE) can be written in the form

$$\mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_c w_c(\wp) \mathbf{s}_c(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (3.1)$$

where c denotes a subscript for a cluster. For words construction, a cluster represents a sentence and for sentences construction a cluster represents a section. Here, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is the model $p \times 1$ vector parameter to be estimated, \sum_c denote the sum over all the population clusters, and $\mathbf{s}_c(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is a p -dimensional vector-valued function of the variable of interest and auxiliary variable. Also, $w_c(\wp) = a_c/\pi_c$ denotes the sampling weights attached to cluster c , a_c is the sample \wp membership indicator variable for cluster c , $\pi_c = E_\wp(a_c)$ is the inclusion probability for cluster c , and E_\wp denotes expectation with respect to the sampling design. The solution to (3.1) obtained by a Newton-Raphson-type iterative method gives the estimator $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ of the census parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}_N$ and of the model parameter of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Under cluster sampling design

$$\mathbf{s}_c(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{l=1}^{m_c} \mathbf{s}_{l;c}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \quad (3.2)$$

with

$$\mathbf{s}_{l;c}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \partial \log f(l|c) / \partial \boldsymbol{\theta},$$

where m_c denotes the size of cluster c , l denotes a subscript for an element of cluster c and $f(l|c)$ is the probability density function of obtaining string l of cluster c . For words construction, c represents a sentence, l represents a word, and $f(l|c) = \Pr(\mathbf{R}_l = \mathbf{r}_l)$ is given by (2.1).

3.2 Parameter Estimation

First, we define probability of selection as being

$$p_{i;cl}^{(t)} = e_{i;cl}^{(t)} \frac{\exp(\mathbf{v}_{i;cl}^{(t)T} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{(t)})}{\sum_{i=1}^M e_{i;cl}^{(t)} \exp(\mathbf{v}_{i;cl}^{(t)T} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{(t)})}, i = 1, \dots, M.$$

Then, we decompose the expression $\mathbf{s}_{l;c}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ in (3.2) into two components

$$\mathbf{s}_{l;c}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{s}_{l;c}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) + \mathbf{s}_{l;c}(\boldsymbol{\beta})$$

with $\mathbf{s}_{l;c}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \sum_t \sum_{i=1}^M \delta \{ e_{i;cl}^{(t)} \log q_{i;cl}^{(t)} + (1 - e_{i;cl}^{(t)}) \log (1 - q_{i;cl}^{(t)}) \} | \delta \boldsymbol{\alpha}$,

and $\mathbf{s}_{l;c}(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \sum_t \sum_{i=1}^M \delta \{ e_{i;cl}^{(t)} \mathbf{1}_{i;cl}^{(t)} \mathbf{v}_{i;cl}^{(t)T} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{(t)} - e_{i;cl}^{(t)} \exp(\mathbf{v}_{i;cl}^{(t)T} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{(t)}) \} | \delta \boldsymbol{\beta}$,

where $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\boldsymbol{\alpha}^T, \boldsymbol{\beta}^T)^T$ is unknown vector parameter to be estimated, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is the vector parameter associated with the probability of eligibility, and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the vector parameter associated with the probability of selection.

3.3 Variance Derivation and Estimation

We use the linearization approach of Demnati and Rao (2004, 2010) to derive variances and variance estimators. We first give a brief account of the Demnati–Rao (DR) approach. Let d_c be a random weight and $\mathbf{u}_c = (u_{1;c}, \dots, u_{p;c})^T$ be a $p \times 1$ vector of constants for $c = 1, \dots, N$, where N denotes the size of the population. Let $\hat{\mathbf{U}} = \sum_c d_c \mathbf{u}_c$ be a linear combination and, using an operator notation, let $V(\mathbf{u})$ and $\vartheta(\mathbf{u})$ denote respectively the variance of $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ and its variance estimator. Here, \sum_c denotes sum over all population elements. DR expressed an estimator $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ and its induced parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta} = E(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$ as $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = f(\mathbf{d})$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = f(\boldsymbol{\eta})$, where \mathbf{d} is a $N \times 1$ vector with c^{th} component d_c , $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ is a $N \times 1$ vector with c^{th} component $\eta_c = E(d_c)$ and E denotes expectation under random processes involved. The DR linearization variance and variance estimator of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = f(\mathbf{d})$ are simply given by $V_{DR}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = V(\mathbf{z})$ and $\vartheta_{DR}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = \vartheta(\mathbf{z})$ respectively, where $V(\mathbf{z})$ is obtained from $V(\mathbf{u})$ by replacing \mathbf{u}_c by $\mathbf{z}_c = \partial f(\mathbf{b}) / \partial b_c |_{b=\eta}$ and $\vartheta(\mathbf{z})$ is obtained from $\vartheta(\mathbf{u})$ by replacing \mathbf{u}_c by $\mathbf{z}_c = \partial f(\mathbf{b}) / \partial b_c |_{b=d}$, where \mathbf{b} is a $N \times 1$ vector of arbitrary real numbers with c^{th} component b_c .

The design-based variance of the total $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ is given

$$V(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_c \sum_{c'} \mathbf{u}_c \mathbf{u}_{c'}^T (1 - \omega_{c;c'}) / \omega_{c;c'}, \quad (3.2)$$

where $\omega_{c;c'} = \pi_c \pi_{c'} / \pi_{c;c'}$, and $\pi_{c;c'}$ is the joint inclusion probability. A design-based variance estimator of the total $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ is

$$\vartheta_{\wp}(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_c \sum_{c'} w_c(\wp) w_{c'}(\wp) (1 - \omega_{c;c'}) \mathbf{u}_c \mathbf{u}_{c'}^T. \quad (3.3)$$

Consider now the population parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}_N$ defined as solution to ‘‘census’’ estimating equation of the form

$$\mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_N) = \sum_c \mathbf{s}_c(\boldsymbol{\theta}_N) = \mathbf{0}.$$

where $\mathbf{s}_c(\boldsymbol{\theta}_N)$ is a $p \times 1$ dimensional vector-valued function of the known parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and others characteristics. For the linear and logistic regression models, $\mathbf{s}_c(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{x}_c (y_c - \mu_c(\mathbf{x}_c^T \boldsymbol{\theta}))$. A design-based estimator $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ of $\boldsymbol{\theta}_N$ is the solution to following weighted estimating equation

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = \sum_c w_c(\wp) \mathbf{s}_c(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = \mathbf{0}.$$

The DR variance of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is given by $Var_{DR}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = V(\tilde{\mathbf{z}})$, with $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_c = \partial f(\mathbf{b}) / \partial b_c |_{\mathbf{b}=\boldsymbol{\eta}}$. Taking the derivatives of $f(\mathbf{b})$ and evaluating it at $\mathbf{b} = \boldsymbol{\eta}$, we get

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_c = \{\mathbf{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_N)\}^{-1} \mathbf{s}_c(\boldsymbol{\theta}_N). \quad (3.4)$$

where $\mathbf{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_N) = -\partial \mathbf{S}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_N) / \partial \boldsymbol{\theta}_N$. The DR design-based variance of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is given by (3.2) with \mathbf{u}_c replaced by $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_c$ given by (3.4).

Similarly, the DR variance estimator of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is given by $\vartheta_{DR}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = \vartheta(\mathbf{z})$, with $\mathbf{z}_c = \partial f(\mathbf{b}) / \partial b_c |_{\mathbf{b}=\mathbf{d}}$. Taking the derivatives of $f(\mathbf{b})$ and evaluating it at $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{d}$, we get

$$\mathbf{z}_c = \{\hat{\mathbf{J}}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}})\}^{-1} \mathbf{s}_c(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}), \quad (3.5)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{J}}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) = -\partial \hat{\mathbf{S}}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) / \partial \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$. The DR design-based variance estimator of the estimator $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is given by (3.3) with \mathbf{u}_c replaced by \mathbf{z}_c given by (3.5).

The total variance, comprising both the sampling variance and the variance introduced by the sequential element selection process, can be derived in accordance with the methodology specified in the Demnati and Rao (2010) document. Details are omitted for simplicity.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

We parameterize the probability of selection of cluster c in the sample \wp as $\pi_c = \{lb + ub \times \exp(\mathbf{v}_{\wp;c}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma})\} / \{1 + \exp(\mathbf{v}_{\wp;c}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma})\}$, where lb and ub are respectively the lower and upper bounds with

$0 < lb < ub \leq 1$, $\mathbf{v}_{\wp;c}$ is the $q_{\wp} \times 1$ vector of explanatory variables and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ is the $q_{\wp} \times 1$ unknown vector parameter to be determined. It is common practice to set $(lb, ub) = (0,1)$. In the case of $\Lambda (> 1)$ parameters of interest, let θ_{κ} denote the parameter of interest κ , $\kappa = 1, \dots, \Lambda$. To create a design, we optimize the conditional expected global cost,

$$\min_{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} \bar{C} = c + \sum_c \pi_c c_c,$$

subject to constraints on Λ variances:

$$V_{DR}(\hat{\theta}_{\kappa}) \leq V_{\kappa}, \kappa = 1, \dots, \Lambda,$$

where c is the overall cost, c_c is the sampling cost for cluster c , V_{κ} are specified tolerances, and $V_{DR}(\hat{\theta}_{\kappa})$ is the DR variance of the estimator $\hat{\theta}_{\kappa}$ for the κ^{th} parameter of interest $\kappa = 1, \dots, \Lambda$. For example, one could specify an upper limit, \mathfrak{S}_{κ} , on the coefficient of variation of $\hat{\theta}_{\kappa}$ so that $V_{\kappa} = \{\mathfrak{S}_{\kappa} E(\hat{\theta}_{\kappa})\}^2$. One may repeat the optimization process with different value of \mathfrak{S}_{κ} $\kappa = 1, \dots, \Lambda$ to obtain the desired minimum cost.

Concluding Remarks

We proposed a simple yet theoretically justified approach to modeling the process of a language. The approach is hierarchical and conditioned on past observed outcomes. We estimate the model parameters along with their associated variance. The proposed approach allows us to analyze when a specific item is most likely to occur and how the selection probability evolves over successive trials. The cost of the estimation step is reduced through sampling.

To address questions regarding the applicability of our approach to computer translation, we begin by slightly extending our initial notation. Suppose a finite population $\mathbf{M}^{(l,j)}$ consists of elements at level l for language j . At the first stage ($l = 1$), the population $\mathbf{M}^{(l,j)}$ comprises all the characters that constitute language j . At the second stage ($l = 2$), $\mathbf{M}^{(l,j)}$ represents the set of all words in language j , and so on for higher levels. Each element $i^{(l,j)}$ in the population $\mathbf{M}^{(l,j)}$ is associated with a vector $\mathbf{x}_i^{(l,j)}$ of explanatory variables that characterize the element. For example, $i^{(1,j)}$ refers to a character in language j , $i^{(2,j)}$ refers to a word, $i^{(3,j)}$ refers to a sentence, and so forth.

The objective of translation is to convey, in a second language, the meaning derived from reading a text in a first language - even if the true meaning is likely unobservable. This task which consists of translating a text written in any language is complex for several reasons, including: (1) The true meaning is unknown, and any linguistic expression is merely an approximation of the original idea; (2) The translation of a given element may depend on other elements dispersed throughout the text; and, (3) Multiple valid translations

may exist for a single element, and selecting among them depends on the intended meaning—which, again, is not directly observable.

We may decompose the joint distribution $f(i^{(l,1)}, i^{(l,2)})$ as

$$f(i^{(l,1)}, i^{(l,2)}) = f(i^{(l,1)})f(i^{(l,2)}|i^{(l,1)}),$$

where $f(i^{(l,j)})$ is the marginal distribution studied previously in this document. The remaining extra-step is to estimate the parameters of the conditional distribution $f(i^{(l,2)}|i^{(l,1)})$, which—like the marginal distributions of the two languages—is also multinomial in nature.

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